

Proficient photo catalytic degradation of methylene blue and methyl orange dyes as organic pollutant from aqueous medium

Tajamal Hussain^{1, €}, Sidrah Ishaq[§], Azeem Intisar^{2, ≡}, Adnan Mujahid^{*}, Ejaz Ahmed[¶], Ahsan Sharif[◇]

Institute of Chemistry, University of the Punjab, Lahore-54590, Pakistan.

To cite this article:

Tajamal Hussain, Sidrah Ishaq, Azeem Intisar, Adnan Mujahid, Ejaz Ahmed, Ahsan Sharif. “Proficient photo catalytic degradation of methylene blue and methyl orange dyes as organic pollutant from aqueous medium”, *Parana Journal of Science and Education*, Vol. 4, No. 7, **2018**, pp. 17-23.

Received: October 04, 2018; **Accepted:** October 23, 2018; **Published:** October 25, 2018.

Abstract

Because of the distinctive and fascinating properties of metal nanoparticles, their synthesis and applications in variety of fields have augmented a great devotion. In this research, facile approaches have been adopted for the synthesis of nanoparticles to be used as photocatalyst to decompose organic hazardous pollutants. Nanoparticles of Ag and ZnO are synthesized by wet chemical reduction of salt and direct precipitation method respectively. Synthesis of the nanoparticles has been characterized by UV-Visible and FTIR spectroscopy. Functionality of the prepared nanoparticles is studied by photo catalytic oxidation, decomposition, of organic pollutants, methylene blue and methyl orange by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Comparison of catalytic activity of metal nanoparticles on oxidation of dyes revealed that Ag nanocatalysts are more effective in photo catalytic oxidation of both dyes.

Keywords: Photo catalyst, Catalytic activity, Oxidation of dye, Methylene blue, Methyl orange.

[€] E-mail: tajamalhussain.chem@pu.edu.pk, tjm199@hotmail.com ¹(Corresponding author 1)

[§] E-mail: ishagsidrah@yahoo.com

[≡] E-mail: azeemintisar.chem@pu.edu.pk ²(Corresponding author 2)

^{*} E-mail: adnanmujahid.chem@pu.edu.pk

[¶] E-mail: dr.ejaz.ahmed@gmail.com

[◇] E-mail: chahsansharif@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

Due to remarkable structural, optical as well as catalytic properties of nanoparticles, these find their uses in various fields like sensing, optical switching and as catalysis [1-3]. Large surface energy, quantum confinement and plasmon excitation are main features of metal nanoparticles. For the uses of metal nanoparticles in different fields, their size controlling is important. They, in nanoscale, possess size dependent characteristics unlike bulk materials [2]. They have been used as photo catalysts in decomposition of many organic pollutants in wastewater at ambient temperature and pressure [3]. Metal nanoparticles are finding their uses in heterogeneous catalysis for over 50 years [4-5]. In heterogeneous catalysis, metal nanoparticles are used in oxidation and hydrogenation reactions. Numerous chemical reactions are thus carried out in the presence of nanoparticles as catalysts [6-7]. Several catalytic applications of metal nanoparticles are covered in many recent reviews [8-12]. Topic of present work is based upon the method of synthesis, catalytic applications as well as unique properties of Ag and Zn nanocatalysts [13]. They are being used in catalysis because of their large surface area, stability and greater number of atoms present on the surface [14]. They show excellent photo catalytic properties [15-16]. Mostly, silver nanoparticles [17], gold [18], platinum [19] and palladium [20] are being used in the field of catalysis. Serious ecological damage is being caused by the extensive use of organic dyes. Therefore, developments made to degrade these dyes have gained greater importance. In this regard, metal nanoparticles due to having large surface area to volume ratio play a vital role in photo catalytic degradation of such dyes. By gaining the achievements of desired and interested properties, catalyst's efficiency can be improved to make the system more economical. As a result, field of nanocatalysts looks very hopeful and promising to work on.

In present work, ZnO nanoparticles are synthesized by using cost efficient direct precipitation method where urea was used as a precipitating agent that helped in controlling particle size and dispersion in the solution [21]. For the synthesis of Ag nanoparticles, chemical reduction method is well carried out because this approach has many

advantages such as no other stabilizing agent is required [22-23]. Both of these methods are less time consuming to get the nanoscale particles. Catalytic applications of prepared Ag and ZnO nanoparticles were then studied in photo catalytic oxidation of organic dyes, methylene blue and methyl orange. Characterization of synthesized nanoparticles was carried out by using FTIR and UV-Visible spectroscopy.

2. Experimental

2.1 Chemicals and instruments

All chemicals glucose (Glaxo), silver nitrate (B.D.H), methylene blue (Panreac), methyl orange (Riedel), urea (Sigma Aldrich), zinc nitrate Hexahydrate (Merck) were used as purchased.

Centrifuge machine was used for separation of nanoparticles. Absorbance was noted by UV-Visible spectrometer (T90+) from PG instruments Ltd. Oven (BINDER) was used to dry the particles. Ultra sonicator (Supersonic X3) was used to disperse the nanoparticles and FTIR spectrometer (Cary 630) of Agilent Technologies was used for characterization of synthesized materials.

2.2 Synthesis of Ag nanocatalyst

For the synthesis of Ag nanoparticles, 0.01M solution of silver nitrate was added drop wise with the help of pipette in the solution of glucose. Solution of glucose was prepared by dissolving 2 g of glucose in 40-45mL water. This mixture was then kept in water bath for 3-4 hours at ~70-75°C. Solution was sonicated for half an hour. After that, centrifugation of the solution was done for 10 minutes to settle down Ag nanoparticles. Nanoparticles were kept in oven for 5 minutes to be dried.

2.3 Synthesis of ZnO nanocatalyst

Zinc nitrate solution (50mL, 0.5 M) was kept under constant stirring for about 30 minutes for complete homogeneity. Similarly, 50 mL of urea solution (1M) was also placed on magnetic stirrer for constant

stirring. In this procedure, urea acted as precipitating agent and added drop wise into the solution of zinc nitrate at $\sim 70^{\circ}\text{C}$ with vigorous stirring. It took two hours for the complete growth of nanoparticles. The precipitating solution was whitish cloudy in appearance. Solution was centrifuged for 10 min and washed with distilled water to remove possible absorbed ions or any impurities.

2.4 Catalytic Activity for Oxidation of methylene blue and methyl orange dyes using Ag and ZnO Catalysts

In order to investigate the catalytic activity of prepared nanocatalysts, Ag and ZnO, photo catalytic oxidation of methylene blue and methyl orange was selected as a model reaction. UV-Visible absorption spectrum was used to study the catalytic activities of synthesized nanoparticles. For kinetic studies, absorbance values were recorded at different time intervals with and without addition of nanocatalysts. Solution of methylene blue dye was prepared by dissolving 0.9 mg of dye in 100 mL of de-ionized water. While solution of methyl orange dye was prepared by dissolving 0.8 mg of dye in 100 mL of water. Absorbance of the solutions was noted with and without addition of catalysts at λ_{max} of the respective dyes. With the passage of time, decrease in absorbance at λ_{max} (460 nm for methylene blue and 665 nm for methyl orange) was observed for both dyes.

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Synthesis of ZnO and Ag nanoparticles

Figure 1. UV-Visible spectrum of ZnO nanoparticles.

Figure 2. FTIR spectrum of ZnO nanoparticles.

Figure 3. UV-Visible spectrum of Ag nanoparticles.

Synthesized nanoparticles of ZnO and Ag have been characterized by UV-Visible and FTIR spectroscopy. UV-Visible and FTIR spectra of ZnO are given in Figures (1) and (2), respectively. As obvious from the spectrum, λ_{max} for ZnO was observed at 375 nm. It is reported in the literature that λ_{max} of the spherical shape and well crystallized nanoparticles is around 378 nm λ_{max} observed for ZnO in present case is well agreed with the reported value. Moreover, FTIR spectrum of the ZnO was also support the synthesis ZnO nanoparticles. Presence of characteristic peak at 522 cm^{-1} corresponding to stretching of metal-oxygen bond confirms the presence of ZnO. UV-Visible spectrum of Ag nanoparticles is given in Figure (3) in λ_{max} value of synthesized Ag nanoparticles is observed around 420 nm and value reported in the literature for such system was in the range of 400-

420 nm. This indicates the synthesis of the Ag nanoparticles.

3.2 Stability of the methylene blue and methyl orange dyes

Figure 4. UV-Visible spectra of methyl orange solution without catalyst immediately after solution formation and 30 min exposure to sunlight to check the stability.

Figure 5. UV-Visible spectra of methylene blue solution without catalyst immediately after solution formation and 30 min exposure to sunlight to check the stability.

Photo catalytic activity of the synthesized catalyst has been studied for photodecomposition of methylene blue and methyl orange dye. Time resolved studies has been done using window of 30 min. In order to check the stability of the dyes in this time frame, solution of the dyes have been exposed the for 30 min and UV-Visible spectra were recorded and compared with those of before light exposition given in Figures (4) and (5) for both dyes.

3.3 Photo-oxidation of methylene blue and methyl orange dyes catalyzed by Ag and ZnO nanocatalysts

In order to study the catalytic activity of prepared catalysts, these catalysts were used in photo oxidation of methylene blue and methyl orange dyes. For this purpose, time resolved degradation of methylene blue and methyl orange dyes has been studied in the presence of Ag and ZnO nanocatalyst and results are displayed in Figures (6-9). As it is obvious from Figures (4) and (5) that dyes are, stable and do not decompose even after the exposure of sunlight for 30 min. However, when the same solution brought to sunlight in the presence of prepared nanocatalyst, Ag and ZnO nanoparticles, decomposition of the methylene blue and methyl orange dyes started and decomposition was recorded in terms of UV-Visible absorption spectrum. Decrease in the intensity of the dye in the absorption spectrum represents the photodecomposition of methylene blue and methyl orange dyes.

An overall comparison of the catalytic efficiency of the synthesized Ag and ZnO nanoparticles for photodecomposition of methylene blue and methyl orange has been done and given in Figure (10). As far as the catalytic ability of both the catalysts is concerned, it can be observed that Ag nanoparticles are more efficiently played its role in decomposition of dyes than that of ZnO nanoparticles. Moreover, Ag more effectively decomposes methylene blue as compared to methyl orange dyes while ZnO nanoparticles showed same efficiency for both the dyes.

Figure 6. Time resolved of decomposition methylene blue in the presence of Ag nanoparticles as catalyst.

Figure 7. Time resolved decomposition of methylene blue in the presence of ZnO NPs as catalyst.

Figure 8. Time resolved decomposition of methyl orange in the presence of Ag Nanoparticles.

Figure 9. Time resolved decomposition of methyl orange in the presence of ZnO nanoparticles.

Figure 10. Comparison between catalytic activity of Ag and ZnO nanoparticles.

3.4 Kinetic study and reaction mechanism

For photo catalytic oxidation process, both the catalyst and the visible light are necessary. When catalyst absorbs the visible radiation, particles of nanocatalysts form a hole (h^+) and an electron (e^-) in valence band and conduction band respectively [24]. By the production of this hole in valence band, molecules of water in dye solution get oxidized and strong oxidant free radicals are generated by this mechanism. Oxidation of dye takes place via series of reactions, which are started or initiated by free hydroxyl radical on catalyst surface. Such mechanism is regarded as “photo catalytic oxidation”. It is suggested that potential occurs for the oxidation of organic dyes by using high intensity sunlight. Excited photosensitizer (dye) can donate or receive the electron depending upon environmental conditions. Under sunlight, dye absorbed on the surface of catalyst may transfer electron to the conduction band of the nanoparticles. This is called photosensitized mechanism.

Dyes absorb on the nanoparticle surface more strongly in visible range. Mechanism, which takes place as follows: (PC stands for photo catalyst).

In order to well explain the sun light induced oxidation by photo catalyst, the mechanism known as photosensitizing oxidation is also studied according to which when dye is in excited form, it losses the

electron to produce cation radical at the catalyst surface and thus reaction occurs as follows to produce byproducts. (4-6)

Therefore, it can be said that both type of mechanisms are taking place during the reaction. For photo catalytic oxidation reaction, the catalyst go in excited state and then produces the free radical oxidant whereas, in case of photosensitizing oxidation mechanism, however hydroxyl radical is formed but in this case, dye is excited via visible light and gives electron to catalyst conduction band. Overall, it is hard to say that what kind of mechanism is more superior to other one.

4. Conclusions

In presented exertion, two types of metal nanoparticles are synthesized and their catalytic behavior is studied in photo catalytic oxidation of two dyes. The nanoscale Ag nanoparticles (9nm) are generated via reduction of salt and ZnO (19nm) nanoscale catalysts are prepared via direct precipitation method. Promising results are achieved in both cases with Ag photo catalyst when it was used in photo oxidation of dyes under sunlight and its catalytic activity is compared with the catalytic activity of ZnO nanoparticle, which is high for Ag. Kinetics studies confirmed that reaction order for the photo oxidation of dyes is first order. In this way, Ag nanoparticles can be used as more effective catalyst in detoxification of water from organic contaminants. With the improvement of such type of catalyst, revolution can be deliberated for heterogeneous photo catalysis with the help of visible light in large scale in order to report water polluted with organic content.

References

[1] W. Gotschy, K. Vonmetz, A. Leitner, F. Aussenegg, "Optical dichroism of lithographically designed silver nanoparticle films", *Opt. Lett.*, 21, **1996**, 1099-1101.

[2] R. Pool, "Clusters: Strange Morsels of Matter: When metals or semiconductors are shrunk down to clumps only 10 or 100 atoms in size, they become a" totally new class of materials" with potentially valuable applications", *Science* (New York, NY), **1990**.

[3] H. Inouye, K. Tanaka, I. Tanahashi, T. Hattori and H. Nakatsuka, "Ultrafast optical switching in a silver nanoparticle system", *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.*, 39, **2000**, 5132.

[4] R. Raja, S. Hermans, D. S. Shephard, B. F. G. Johnson, R. Raja, G. Sankar, S. Bromley, J. M. Thomas, "Preparation and characterisation of a highly active bimetallic (Pd–Ru) nanoparticle heterogeneous catalyst", *Chemical Communications*, 16, **1999**, 1571-1572.

[5] Elad Gross, F. Toste, G. Somorjai, "Polymer-encapsulated metallic nanoparticles as a bridge between homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis", *Catalysis Letters*, 145.1, **2015**, 126-138.

[6] M. Reetz, W. Helbig, "Size-selective synthesis of nanostructured transition metal clusters", *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **1994**, 116, 16, 7401-7402.

[7] D. Astruc, F. Lu, J. Aranzas, "Nanoparticles as recyclable catalysts: the frontier between homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis", *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, **2005**, 7852-7872.

[8] A. Roucoux, J. Schulz, and H. Patin, "Reduced transition metal colloids: a novel family of reusable catalysts?", *Chemical Reviews*, 102, 10, **2002**, 3757-3778.

[9] J. Aiken and R. Finke, "A review of modern transition-metal nanoclusters: their synthesis, characterization, and applications in catalysis", *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical*, 145, 1, **1999**, 1-44.

[10] L. Ott, and R. Finke, "Transition-metal nanocluster stabilization for catalysis: a critical review of ranking methods and putative stabilizers", *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, 251, 9, **2007**, 1075-1100.

[11] R. Narayanan, and M. El-Sayed, "Catalysis by metallic nanoparticles: the good and the bad", *Chimica oggi*, 25, 1, **2007**, 84-86.

[12] Y. Pan, et al. "Size-dependent cytotoxicity of gold nanoparticles", *Small*, 3, 11, **2007**, 1941-1949.

[13] R. Finke, "Transition-metal nanoclusters: solution-phase synthesis, then characterization and mechanism of formation, of polyoxoanion and tetrabutylammoniumstabilized nanoclusters", *Metal nanoparticles: synthesis, characterization and applications*, New York, **2002**, 17-54.

[14] L. Lewis, "Chemical catalysis by colloids and clusters", *Chemical Reviews*, 93, 8, **1993**, 2693-2730.

[15] R. Pool, "Clusters: Strange Morsels of Matter: When metals or semiconductors are shrunk down to clumps only 10 or 100 atoms in size, they become a" totally new class of materials" with potentially valuable applications", *Science* (New York, NY), **1990**, 1186-1188.

[16] P. Sahoo, et al. "Synthesis of silver nanoparticles using facile wet chemical route", *Defence Science Journal*, 59, 4, **2009**, 447-455

[17] V. Vidhu and Daizy Philip, "Catalytic degradation of organic dyes using biosynthesized silver nanoparticles", *Micron*, 56, **2014**, 54-62.

[18] A. Pich, et al., "Tuneable catalytic properties of hybrid microgels containing gold nanoparticles", *Journal of nanoscience and nanotechnology*, 6, 12, **2006**, 3763-3769.

[19] Y. Mei, et al., "High catalytic activity of platinum nanoparticles immobilized on spherical polyelectrolyte brushes", *Langmuir*, 21, 26, **2005**, 12229-12234.

[20] Y. Mei, et al., "Catalytic activity of palladium nanoparticles encapsulated in spherical polyelectrolyte brushes and core-shell microgels" *Chemistry of Materials*, 19, 5, **2007**, 1062-1069.

[21] S. Bagheri, K. Chandrappa, S. Hamid, "Facile synthesis of nano-sized ZnO by direct precipitation method, IPS Building, University of Malaya", *Nanotechnology & Catalysis Research Centre (NANOCAT)*, **2013** 265-270

[22] Sudipa Panigrahi, et al. "General method of synthesis for metal nanoparticles", *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 6.4, **2004**, 411-414.

[23] R Augustine and K. Rajarathinam "Synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles and its immobilization on aliginate coated sutures for the

prevention of surgical wound infections and the in vitro release studies" *International journal of nano dimension*, 2, 3 **2012**, 205-12

[24] G. Epling, C. Lin, "Photoassisted bleaching of dyes utilizing TiO₂ and visible light", *Chemosphere*, 46, 4, **2002**, 561-570.